

THE IMPORTANCE OF ENCOURAGING STUDENTS TO LEARN LANGUAGES.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10444624>

Annotation: People have several different reasons to learn a foreign language; people often learn a language for practical reasons while others have a particular love for the language and its people. So in this article gives information about the importance of encouraging students to learn languages.

Key words: encouragement, motivation, motivational theories, language learning and teaching,

Motivation plays a key role in all facets and types of learning. But it's perhaps most important in language learning, where progress can be difficult to see on a day-to-day basis. Learners with a positive attitude to their course and their studies are more likely to continue working hard and to keep going when times are tough. Although not everyone who is motivated to learn does eventually achieve their goal, many learners who do are frequently highly motivated individuals.

Here are 7 effective strategies for inspiring students and maintaining their motivation for learning new languages.

1. Understand your students' motivations. In order for an educator to motivate a student, it's important that they understand the learner's motivation for learning languages in the first place. The extensive research investigating the link between language learning and motivation identifies two main types of motivation. Some learners have an intrinsic motivation for learning – they want to learn a language because of an internal force to do so. Usually they have an interest in the language or they just love learning or are perhaps more open to self-improvement. On the other hand, extrinsic motivation is powered by an external source. Learners are studying a language for a particular purpose – to get a job, a qualification, to travel or perhaps because a parent has sent them to language school to study!

2. Prioritise pair and group work. One of the most motivating ways to learn a language is through close collaboration and communication with other students, giving learners the opportunity to practice their communication skills. In turn, one of the quickest ways to demotivate a student is to minimise their

participation and involvement. Students learn best by speaking, listening, making, writing, creating and solving – ie. in the active learning mode instead of passive learning. Small-group activities and pair work facilitate these active learning opportunities and boosting self-confidence can also increase their motivation to learn. They also allow all students (even the quietest ones) to express their ideas and working cooperatively can also reduce behaviour incidents and build a mutually supportive classroom environment.

3. Create the right classroom environment. Creating a classroom environment that is conducive to learning and where students feel able to grow and succeed is clearly a key element in building students' motivation. Allowing students to personalise their learning space can also have a positive, motivational effect.

One key element to consider is where students sit and how the classroom is oriented. Wherever possible, try to create a layout which maximises eye contact, both between teacher and student and also between students. Linked to this, it's important that students are all physically included and that no-one is sitting alone or outside pairs / groups. The classroom also needs space for students to move from group to group, but not so much space that the atmosphere is quiet and there's little engagement in the lesson.

4. Provide a clear path of success. Professor Zoltán Dörnyei from Nottingham University is an expert in motivation studies. [His work in the field](#) has clearly identified that learners who are able to construct clear mental images of themselves as successful second language speakers tend to more often achieve their goals.

5. Personalise learning and give students agency. When students are offered choice and flexibility in their learning, they are more clearly able to see and feel that it has been tailored and personalised to their individual learning styles. Students then feel that they have licence to say what they want to say and how they want to say it. Educators who offer this flexibility motivate learners to go the extra mile and make more than expected progress.

6. Keep everything relevant and usable in real life. Whatever their core motivation for learning a language, all students want to feel that the learning activities they undertake are interesting, meaningful and relevant. It is important that they are learning skills that are designed to be used and that they are not just learning for learning's sake.

7. Give always feedback. Most language learners want to succeed, so the careful use of praise and positive feedback can be powerful motivators to encourage their continued progress. As outlined at the beginning of this

post, students can find it difficult to see the progress that they're making or where they need extra support / work. So there's an important role for language educators to play in providing that guide – marking assignments and detailing where improvement can be made is clearly a key part of this work.

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